

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF BENZIL SEMICARBAZONE COMPLEXES

Compounds	$\Delta\nu$ mhos. cm^2	% Metal		% halogen, thiocyanate or nitrogen		μ_{eff} B.M.
		Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	
1. MnCl_2	10.9	13.58	13.98	17.81	18.07	5.9
2. $\text{MnL}(\text{NCS})_2$	8.4	13.32	12.55	26.21	26.49	5.8
3. $\text{MnL}(\text{NO}_2)_2$	10.2	12.15	12.32	15.54	15.70	5.8
4. $\text{MnL}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$	10.5	10.36	10.55	7.78	8.06	5.9
5. CoL_2Cl_2	11.2	8.71	8.93	10.38	10.69	4.9
6. $\text{CoL}_2(\text{SCN})_2$	9.8	8.14	8.31	16.21	16.36	5.1
7. $\text{CoL}_2(\text{NO}_2)_2$	7.9	8.05	8.22	15.45	15.62	5.0
8. $[\text{CoL}_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$	245	7.25	7.44	10.28	10.60	4.9
9. NiLCl_2	10.2	14.51	14.30	17.59	17.90	Diamag.
10. $\text{NiL}(\text{SCN})_2$	11.4	13.08	13.29	26.02	26.26	"
11. $\text{NiL}(\text{NO}_2)_2$	9.4	12.82	13.06	15.25	15.57	"
12. CuL_2Cl_2	11.5	9.21	9.50	10.43	10.62	1.78
13. $\text{CuL}_2(\text{SCN})_2$	11.2	8.45	8.90	16.11	16.26	1.79
14. $\text{CuL}_2(\text{NO}_2)_2$	12.8	8.54	8.80	15.34	15.52	1.81
15. ZnLCl_2	11.8	16.02	16.21	17.28	17.60	—
16. $\text{ZnL}(\text{SCN})_2$	12.5	14.25	14.58	25.48	25.87	—
17. $\text{ZnL}(\text{NO}_2)_2$	10.8	14.16	14.33	15.21	15.34	—
18. CdL_2Cl_2	9.4	15.42	15.67	9.72	9.90	—
19. $[\text{CdL}_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$	242	13.12	13.30	9.75	9.94	—
20. $[\text{ZnL}_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$	235	7.85	8.19	10.35	10.52	—

L - Benzil semicarbazone

TABLE 2—SPECTRAL DATA OF SOME COMPLEXES

Compound No.	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{N}-\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$	ν_{max} in kK (ϵ)
1	1630	1580	1015	460	320	20.4(1), 22.0(2), 24.5(2)
4	1630	1585	1020	465	320	20.2(2), 22.2(2), 24.0(2)
5	1635	1580	1020	470	325	19.8(38), 20.1
8	1630	1590	1020	470	330	19.9(35), 20.4
9	1635	1585	1015	475	330	15.0(58)
12	1630	1580	1020	485	335	14.8(42)
16	1630	1580	1020	480	335	—
19	1635	1585	1015	485	340	—

Magnetic moment values of manganese complexes are in the range of 5.8–5.9 B.M. Cobalt complexes have moments in the range 4.9–5.1 B.M., suggesting an octahedral environment. Nickel complexes are diamagnetic and copper complexes have μ_{eff} values in the range 1.78–1.82 B.M. Infrared spectra of benzil semicarbazone have main absorption bands at 3130, 1655, 1650, 1600 and 1000 cm^{-1} assignable¹⁰ to $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{N}-\text{N})$, respectively. $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ in the complexes remains almost unaffected excepting in the chloro complexes where a lowering of the band occurs possibly due to hydrogen bonding with the anion. $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ is observed around 1630 cm^{-1} along with a shoulder at 1645 cm^{-1} probably indicating¹¹ the coordination through the oxygen atom of one of the carbonyl group, the other carbonyl remaining free. $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ in the complexes also shifts to lower frequency region and is observed around 1580 cm^{-1} suggesting coordination through the azomethine nitrogen atom. This has been further substantiated by the observation¹² of $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ around 460–485 and 320–340 cm^{-1} region. Thus, the ligand behaves as bidentate in all the cases excepting the cobalt perchlorate complex where only one carbonyl absorption is observed. Hence, the ligand in this complex coordinates through the oxygen atoms of both the carbonyl groups and the azomethine

nitrogen atom indicating the tridentate nature of the ligand.

In the thiocyanato complexes $\nu(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$ is found around 2090–2105 cm^{-1} region, showing¹³ the presence of terminal N-bonded thiocyanato group. Nitrate complexes have the ν_1 and ν_4 bands in the 1280 and 1410 cm^{-1} region, respectively. The difference, $\Delta\nu$, is of the order of 130 cm^{-1} suggestive^{14,15} of monodentate nitrate coordination. In the cadmium, zinc and cobalt perchlorate complexes there is one broad absorption band at 1100 cm^{-1} indicating^{16,17} ionic perchlorate group in conformity with the molar conductance data suggestive of 1 : 2 electrolytic nature of the complexes.

In the visible electronic spectra of manganese complexes three absorption bands are observed around 20.0, 22.0 and 24.0 kK regions assignable¹⁸ to ${}^6\text{A}_1 \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_1(\text{G})$, $\rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_2(\text{G})$ and $\rightarrow {}^4\text{A}_1(\text{G})$ transitions respectively. Extinction coefficient values are within 1 and 2. Thus, on the basis of the band positions and intensity, tetrahedral structure is presumed for these complexes. All the cobalt complexes give rise to one absorption band around 19–20 kK region with a shoulder on the high frequency side, attributable¹⁹ to ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ transition, the shoulder may be the consequence of splitting due to spin orbit coupling. Lower energy

bands due to the transition ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ could not be recorded due to limitations of the instrument. Hence, on the basis of the spectral bands, their intensity and magnetic moment values, a spin free octahedral stereochemistry is suggested for these complexes. Nickel complexes exhibit one absorption band around 14.5-15.0 kK region with extinction coefficient values round about sixty. A square planar configuration is assigned²⁰ to these complexes in conformity with the diamagnetic nature of the compounds. All the copper complexes exhibit one broad absorption band in the 14.8-15.5 kK regions indicating a distorted octahedral configuration²¹. On the basis of analysis, conductance and infrared spectral data, the zinc and cadmium complexes have presumably a tetrahedral environment around the metal ions. Thus in case of all the complexes possibly the ligand is bonded to the metal ions at site I and II excepting the cobalt perchlorate complex where the metal ion is bonded at site III in addition to site I and II.

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